

ISic1415

I.Sicily inscription 1415

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

hypogeum XI, Cappuccini catacombs

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. κατὰ τοῦ μελ
2. λητεικοῦ μη
3. δις ἀνοίξη ὦδε
4. ὅτει Νόφειος
5. κὲ Νύφη κείτε.
6. εὐλογί
7. α τοῖς ὀσί
8. οῖς
9. ὦδε.
- 10.

Apparatus

Text of Curbera 1996

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644966

PHI 178076

Bibliography

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